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HYBRID SEM-FEA-EXPERIMENTAL DYNAMIC MODELS OF FRAME STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: The use of a hybrid technique is proposed for modeling frame structures with complex boundary conditions. The hybrid technique consists of combining spectral elements, finite elements, and experimentally obtained impedances. The Spectral Element Method (SEM) is formulated in the frequency domain and is based on exact shape functions, thus providing accurate solutions even at high frequencies without the necessity of mesh refinement, as it is the case with Finite Elements (FE). Nevertheless, the SEM has a relatively poor library of elements. In the proposed hybrid technique, finite elements are used to model the elements that cannot be represented via SEM, and then coupled to the spectral elements. Furthermore, in order to take into account complex boundary conditions, the two elements can be combined with measured impedances. In this paper, the method is illustrated with simple frame structures such as a clamped beam and a beam plunged into a sandbox.

KEYWORDS: Spectral elements, finite elements, hybrid modeling, frame structures, impedance.

INTRODUCTION

Approximate numerical methods, such as Finite Elements (FE) and Boundary Elements (BE), provide a suitable tool for the dynamic analysis of structures and are increasingly being used in the industry. However, the discrepancy between predictions of the dynamical behavior and the real behavior tends to increase with frequency. This discrepancy is usually due to poor discretization of the continuum and/or low of the order of the finite element used, differences in the physical parameters, and poorly represented boundary conditions. Some boundary conditions cannot be easily represented in the numerical models, as it is the case with soil-structure interaction and interaction with the surrounding structures through complex joints.

There is currently a search for methods that would overcome the limitations of the FE analysis at higher frequencies without having to go all the way into a statistical analysis such as SEA [1], where only asymptotical, averaged results (both spatially and in frequency) can be obtained. One trend is to try to combine FE with SEA in a hybrid model [2]. Many researchers are currently investigating the possibilities of this approach, originally shown to work for simple bar structures. Another is to try to simplify the wave equations and solve them with a thermal analogy – the so-called Energy Finite Elements [3]. A third line of current research is to use multiple elementary sources with a simple fundamental solution for an infinite structure to impose arbitrary boundary conditions. The latter can be classified as meshless methods [4,5]. Another approach consists of trying to solve the wave equation for the medium within a simple element and then assemble the elements using the direct stiffness method, so popular due to FE, which we call here the Spectral Element Method (SEM) [6].

SEM is a systematic way of solving structural dynamic problems using a wave-based approach (fundamental solution). Although still limited to relatively simple elements – basically homogeneous frames and flat plates with particular boundary conditions [6] –, it is very easy to implement. The SEM is formulated directly in the frequency domain and yields results that are exact within the framework of the strength of materials theory used

to derive the element. Thus, for homogeneous elements, in contrast to the FE, SEM provides accurate solutions at arbitrarily high frequencies without the necessity of mesh refinement.

In this paper, the formulation of the SEM for frame elements is reviewed and it is shown how some of the limitations of SEM can be overcome if it is combined with FE and experimentally obtained impedances. The use of the proposed methodology is illustrated with the characterization of a clamped beam and a beam plunged into a sandbox.

REVIEW OF SEM

In the literature, spectrally formulated finite and semi-infinite elements known as spectral elements [6] are presented for Timoshenko beams. In contrast to the conventional FE, this formulation provides exact mass distribution within each structural element. In general, a structure is discretized in a small number of spectral elements (one for each span between two discontinuities) and then these elements are assembled using the direct stiffness approach, in an analogous way to that used in FE analysis. The main difference is that the calculations in SEM are all carried out in the frequency domain. Time-domain responses can be obtained by performing an inverse FFT. SEM can be seen as a combination of the exact wave method and the assembling features of FE. Two different types of beam elements can be used in this method: 2-noded and throw-off, the latter being a semi-infinite element. Due to space restrictions, the equations of the SEM for beams are not shown extensively in this paper. For the beam wave-guide obeying the Timoshenko beam theory, the equation of motion will have a four-coefficient exact solution given as,

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\phi}(x) &= \mathbf{A}e^{-ik_1x} + \mathbf{B}e^{-ik_2x} + \mathbf{C}e^{-ik_1(L-x)} + \mathbf{D}e^{-ik_2(L-x)} \\ \hat{v}(x) &= R_1\mathbf{A}e^{-ik_1x} + R_2\mathbf{B}e^{-ik_2x} - R_1\mathbf{C}e^{-ik_1(L-x)} - R_2\mathbf{D}e^{-ik_2(L-x)}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where R_1 and R_2 are defined as the amplitude ratios, k_1 , k_2 are the wave numbers, and \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{D} are constants obtained through the application of the different boundary conditions. For throw-off elements, the equations of motion can easily be established from Eqn. 1 by putting $\mathbf{C}=\mathbf{D}=0$, as waves propagate in only one direction. The solution to these equations can be written in terms of the nodal displacements, and a relation between the global shear forces and moments and the global nodal degrees of freedom can be established as,

$$\left[\hat{\mathbf{K}}_g \right] \left\{ \hat{\mathbf{U}}_g \right\} = \left\{ \hat{\mathbf{F}} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $\left[\hat{\mathbf{K}}_g \right]$ is the global dynamic stiffness matrix, which is symmetric and generally complex. The individual elements of this matrix can be found in [6]. When frame structures are analyzed in three-dimensional space, longitudinal and torsional waves also propagate. To model these kinds of waves, spectral rod and shaft elements must be used. The spectral solutions for the rod and shaft equations of motion are of the same type as $\hat{\phi}$ in Eqn. 1. The fact that only one element is needed between any two discontinuities plays the role of making the number of elements needed to model a structure relatively small when compared to the FE. The solution is accurate independently of element's length, even at higher frequencies. Thus, the response at different nodal degrees of freedom can be recovered with less computational effort, even when solving this system of equations for each frequency line. The use of the frame spectral element for three-dimensional frame structures is shown in detail in [7].

CASE STUDY I: CLAMPED-FREE BEAM

This simple case study is frequently used to verify numerical dynamic analysis methods. The clamped condition of beams is ideally modeled by considering an infinite stiffness at the clamped degrees of freedom (DOF). This boundary condition is imposed simply by eliminating the columns and rows of the mass and stiffness matrices that correspond to the clamped DOF. However, even a very rigid clamping cannot be realistically modeled with this assumption. To show how the clamping conditions can be characterized, consider a straight beam clamped at one end with an excitation applied at a point x along its length, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Scheme of the experimental configuration and SEM model of a clamped-free beam and its DOF.

The beam is discretized into two spectral elements with two DOF at each node. Thus, the global dynamic stiffness matrix is a (6x6) matrix given as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & K_{13} & K_{14} & K_{15} & K_{16} \\ & K_{22} & K_{23} & K_{24} & K_{25} & K_{26} \\ & & K_{33} & K_{34} & K_{35} & K_{36} \\ & & & K_{44} & K_{45} & K_{46} \\ \text{sym.} & & & & K_{55} & K_{56} \\ & & & & & K_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ \phi_1 \\ v_2 \\ \phi_2 \\ v_3 \\ \phi_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -K_{v1}v \\ -K_{\phi1}\phi \\ F \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where the force at node 1 is represented by the translational and rotational dynamic reaction forces $-K_{v1}v_1$ and $-K_{\phi1}\phi_1$, respectively, with K_{v1} and $K_{\phi1}$ defined as translational and rotational dynamic stiffness at node 1. The displacement DOF are classified as follows:

- v_2 and v_3 are the DOF easy to measure
- v_1 and ϕ_1 are the clamped DOF that cannot be measured
- ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 are the DOF that are normally hard to measure

Equation 3 can be written in a simplified form as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} [M_{11}] & [M_{12}] \\ [M_{21}] & [M_{22}] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{U_1\} \\ \{U_2\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{f_1\} \\ \{f_2\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where the different sub-matrices are defined as,

$$\begin{aligned} [M_{11}] &= \begin{bmatrix} K_{13} & K_{15} \\ K_{23} & K_{25} \end{bmatrix}, & [M_{12}] &= \begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & K_{14} & K_{16} \\ K_{21} & K_{22} & K_{24} & K_{26} \end{bmatrix} \\ [M_{21}] &= \begin{bmatrix} K_{33} & K_{35} \\ K_{43} & K_{45} \\ K_{53} & K_{55} \\ K_{63} & K_{65} \end{bmatrix}, & [M_{22}] &= \begin{bmatrix} K_{31} & K_{32} & K_{34} & K_{36} \\ K_{41} & K_{42} & K_{44} & K_{46} \\ K_{51} & K_{52} & K_{54} & K_{56} \\ K_{61} & K_{62} & K_{64} & K_{66} \end{bmatrix} \\ \{U_1\} &= \begin{Bmatrix} v_2 \\ v_3 \end{Bmatrix}, & \{U_2\} &= \begin{Bmatrix} v_1 \\ \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \\ \phi_3 \end{Bmatrix}, & \{f_1\} &= \begin{Bmatrix} -K_{v1}v_1 \\ -K_{\phi1}\phi_1 \end{Bmatrix}, & \{f_2\} &= \begin{Bmatrix} F \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Using the second matrix equation of Eqn. 4, the variables in $\{U_2\}$ can be solved as,

$$\{U_2\} = [M_{22}]^{-1}\{f_2\} - [M_{22}]^{-1}[M_{21}]\{U_1\} \quad (6)$$

and using the first equation of Eqn. 4, the dynamic stiffness K_{v1} and $K_{\phi1}$ that characterize the clamped condition can be solved as,

$$\begin{aligned} \{f_1\} &= [M_{11}]\{U_1\} + [M_{12}]\{U_2\} \\ K_{v1} &= -\frac{\{f_1(1)\}}{v_1}, \quad K_{\phi1} = -\frac{\{f_1(2)\}}{\phi_1} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

These dynamic stiffness can then be used to model the clamping boundary condition (or other types of boundary conditions) by using them instead of the infinite stiffness that are associated with the ideal clamping.

An experiment was performed with aluminum beam with the following properties: $L=0.685\text{m}$, $E=7 \times 10^{10}\text{N/m}^2$, $\rho=2800\text{Kg/m}^3$, $A=25.6 \times 3.3\text{mm}^2$, $I=7.666 \times 10^{-11}\text{m}^4$, $\nu=0.3$, and with a hysteretic damping factor of $\eta=10^{-6}$. A random excitation force was applied by an electro-dynamic shaker at a point $x=0.27\text{m}$ from the clamped end as shown in Fig. 2. A frequency range of 1Hz to 3.2kHz, with a resolution of 3200 frequency lines, was analyzed. The flexural frequency response functions (FRF) were measured at the excitation point and at the free end, by using Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV) with a sensitivity of 40V/m/s. The LDV was connected to a data acquisition system.

Fig. 2: Experimental setup of the clamped-free beam experiment.

The measured FRFs were then used in Eqns. 4 and 7, and the dynamic stiffness of the clamping condition are determined, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Translational and rotational dynamic stiffness of the clamped end obtained using experimental data.

The same beam was modeled via SEM as free-free beam. The characterized dynamic stiffness coefficients were then added to the corresponding DOF of the global matrix, and the FRF at the excitation point was calculated. The clamped condition was also modeled in the usual manner, i.e., by eliminating the rows and columns corresponding to the clamped DOF. A comparison between the different FRFs is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: FRF (DOF: v_2) of the clamped-free beam: measured, computed with ideal clamping, and computed with the experimental impedance.

The result of the experimentally adjusted FRF is shown in Fig. 4. As expected, the current methodology yielded FRFs which are nearly identical to the measured FRFs. On the other hand, the FRF computed using the ideal clamping (canceling columns and rows corresponding to the clamped DOF) shows agreement with the measured FRF only for the first three modes. Beyond this mode, the FRF becomes quite different from the exact one, due to the poor modeling of the clamping boundary condition. This demonstrates the importance of effectively modeling the real boundary conditions in numerical simulations.

CASE STUDY II: STRUCTURE-SOIL COUPLING

Sandboxes are frequently used in structural intensity investigations as quasi-anechoic terminations. Besides, beams plunged into sandboxes can also present a behavior that is similar to that of piles. The same methodology presented and used in the previous section is again used in this case study. For this sake, an aluminum tube plunged into a sandbox with the following properties was used: outer diameter $\phi_1 = 11.175\text{mm}$, inner diameter $\phi_2 = 9.375\text{mm}$, $E = 7 \times 10^{10}\text{N/m}^2$, $\rho = 2800\text{Kg/m}^3$, $\nu = 0.3$ and $\eta = 10^{-6}$. The total length is 1.36m with 1m plunged into the sandbox. The sandbox is a box made of wood and filled with sand, and has the dimensions of $0.3\text{m} \times 0.3\text{m} \times 1\text{m}$. It is important to note that the sand at the beam entrance is made in a conic shape with foam in order to reduce the impedance discontinuity that causes flexural waves reflections at the entrance of the box.

An electro-dynamic shaker was used as an excitation source at a point located $x = 0.19\text{m}$ away from the free end, as shown in Fig. 5. A frequency range of 1Hz to 3.2kHz, with a resolution of 3200 frequency lines, was analyzed.

The FRF was measured at the excitation point using an LDV. The measured FRFs were again used in Eqns. 4 and 7, and the dynamic stiffness representing the sand box are determined and shown in Fig. 6.

The FRF of the beam with free-free condition is then calculated via SEM and adjusted using the identified dynamic stiffness of the corresponding DOF that represent the sand box. Fig. 7 shows that the adjusted FRF is very similar to the measured FRF.

Fig. 5: Experimental setup of the beam in the sand box.

Fig. 6: Translational and rotational dynamic stiffness representing the impedance of the sand box.

Fig. 7: FRF ($DOF:v_2$), measured and numerically adjusted via SEM.

SEM/FE COUPLING

In some cases it is not possible to model structures via SEM only, due to the poor SEM element library. The SEM/FE coupling is then recommended. On the other hand, infinite elements cannot be effectively modeled via FE and, in this case, SEM throw-off element can be coupled to a FEA model. As an example, an infinite straight beam was modeled via SEM and FE. This could easily be modeled via SEM only, by using two spectral elements: one 2-noded and one throw-off element (Fig. 8a). Nevertheless, for the sake of showing the SEM/FE coupling capabilities, element 2 of the beam was modeled via FE [8], as shown in Fig. 8b. A periodic force was applied at point 2 in a frequency range of 1Hz to 1kHz with 1Hz resolution. The FRF was calculated for both cases and are shown in Fig. 9. It can be observed that the two FRFs are similar except at frequencies above 600Hz. This is related to the low number of FEA elements used (20 elements).

Fig. 8: Models of SEM-only elements and SEM/FE coupled elements.

Fig. 9: FRF calculated via SEM only and via SEM/FE coupling.

USING THE THROW-OFF ELEMENT TO APPROXIMATE THE BOUNDARY IMPEDANCE

The throw-off element is an infinite element that can be used to model anechoic terminations or fast transient phenomena that take place before any reflection can be measured. It can also be used to investigate soil-structure interaction problems. To show the effectiveness of the throw-off element in modeling the impedance of a sandbox, the same circular cross-section beam used in the previous section plunged into the same sand box leaving 0.36m of length outside the box. A force was applied at the point 0.36m away from the free end and the FRF was measured at the excitation point. The beam was also modeled via SEM using the throw-off element, as shown in Fig. 10, and the FRF was numerically calculated at the same point. The comparison of the two FRFs is shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 10: SEM model of the sand box using throw-off element.

Fig. 11: Comparison between measured and numerically calculated FRF via SEM.

It can be observed that the difference between the two FRFs is relatively small. The measured FRF shows some peaks at certain frequencies that are not present in the throw-off model. This is due to the fact that part of the flexural waves reflects back at the sand box entrance, while modeling via SEM no reflections were taken into account. In general, the two FRFs have a similar behavior, so that the SEM model of the sandbox impedance could be used in further dynamical analyses.

CONCLUSIONS

Using very simple structures, it was shown that inaccurate modeling of boundary conditions results in poor predictions of the dynamic models. An approach for characterizing boundary conditions in a more realistic way using a spectral element model was presented. For a simple clamped-free beam, the FRF predicted with the SEM model with the identified clamping stiffness compared very well with the measured FRF. The same methodology was used to characterize the dynamic impedance of a sandbox. This kind of boundary condition is usually found in soil-structure interaction problems and structural intensity investigations. It was shown that it is possible to

model the real boundary impedance of the sandbox using a spectral element, known as throw-off element. It was shown that it is straightforward to couple finite elements with spectral elements, thus overcoming - to a certain extent - the handicap of a relatively poor library of spectral elements. The combined use of SEA/FE/experimental impedance constitute a powerful tool for the dynamic analysis of frame structures at higher frequencies, provided that the beam theory used still holds.

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